

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19337135

Bank Capital, Bank Credit and Private Sector Investment in Nigeria: A Disaggregated Analysis

Obi Onyeka Anthony PhD

Banking and Finance Department
Federal Polytechnic Oko, Anambra State, Nigeria
onyeka.obi@federalpolyoko.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The banking sector has the core function of collecting money in forms of savings, current and fixed deposit accounts to create a pool of funds necessary for productive economic activities. The study examined bank capital, bank credit reform and private sector investment in Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the effect of total bank capital base on private sector investment in Nigeria. Assessed the effect of credit to private sector on private sector investment in Nigeria and determine the effect of exchange rate on private sector investment in Nigeria. The study adopted the *ex-post facto* research design because the data already exist in various international and national publications. The data were analyzed with econometric techniques involving Augmented Dicker Fuller tests for unit roots and the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) approach which is capable of handling both stationary at level $I(0)$ and first difference $I(1)$. The result of the analysis revealed that there is a cointegration or long run relationship between bank capital, bank credit reform and private sector investment in Nigeria. Total bank capital has a positive relationship with private sector investment in all the periods. Credit to private sector had positive relationship with private sector investment in all the periods and exchange rate has a significant short-term negative effect on private sector investment in Nigeria. This suggests that a unit increased in exchange rate will bring about fall in the private sector investment within the short term period especially in the first and second year period. This connotes that banking sector is the driver of the private sector investment in Nigeria. An active and efficient banking sector is essential to enhances growth of the private sector of Nigerian economy. Amongst the recommendations is that the monetary authority should frame and implement policies for regular review and increasing or classification of bank capital base. This will inform the nature and level of operations for such banks. Bank management should review their credit profile and propensity to lending on regular bases. The monetary authority on another hand should discourage banks from granting unproductive loans by way of penal charge. The exchange rate reform in Nigeria has being found to lack short run dynamic influence in the private sector.

Keywords: Bank Capital, Bank Credit, Private Sector Investment, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The banking sector has recently witnessed significant reforms and hard choices had to be made to tackle the lingering effects of the global financial crises, which culminated in the contraction of some banks' balance sheets with the attendant economic losses. It is worthy to note that these problems have been surmounted through series of reforms undertaken by the Central Bank of Nigeria (Amaegberi & Krokeyi, 2024). The banking sector reforms and consolidations has been ongoing economic phenomenon. Reforms generally are predicated upon the need for reorientation and repositioning of an existing status quo in order to attain an effective and efficient state. Banking reforms involves several elements that are unique

to each country based on historical, economic and institutional imperatives (Abubakar, 2023). According to Gyrary (2012), the reforms in the banking sector predicted against the backdrop of banking crises due to high undercapitalization of existing banks, weakness in the regulatory and supervisory frame work, weak management practices and the tolerance of deficiencies in the corporate governance behaviors banks.

Banking sector reform refers to a paradigm shift from government repressive control of the monetary policies to a market mechanism of interest rate determination as propounded by Mckinnon-Shaw Theory (1973). This calls for the removal of all forms of government repressive actions that will greatly enhance loanable funds' accumulation through massive savings which will be accessible to the private sector for stimulation and growth of the national economy (Toby & Zaagha 2020 and Sesay & Abdulai, 2017). According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2004), the banking sector reforms in Nigeria were embarked upon to achieve the following objectives: Market liberalization in order to promote efficiency in resources' allocation; great expansion of saving's mobilization base; promotion of private investment and growth through market-based interest rates; improvement of the regulatory and surveillance framework; fostering healthy competitions in the provision of services as well as laying the basis for inflation control and economic growth.

In Nigeria therefore, given several decades of stunted and erratic Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, high inflation rate coupled with very low and unimpressive economic development and standard of living, it became imperative for government not only to restructure the national economy but also liberalize the financial sector through the banking sector reforms (Bawa, Chiebonam & Abdulsalami, 2021). In view of this situation, private sector finds it difficult not only to exert its laudable role as an engine of economic development but also invest and stimulate growth of the national economy. This is simply because private sector investment is greatly hindered by several factors that bordered on government repressive actions which are in collaboration with regulatory authority (Toby & Zaagha, 2020; Sesay & Abdulai, 2017).

Financial repression, therefore refer to a high level of government interventions in the banking sector and financial markets by setting up ceilings on nominal interest rate, imposing high statutory cash reserves and liquidity requirements on banks, direct interventions on credit allocations to banks, excessive annual domestic borrowings and spending to finance trillions of naira deficit budgets that often crowd out private sector investment (Obi, Ezeabasili, Akamobo and Nwogwugwu, 2021; Jhingan, 2011; Daily Independent Newspapers, 2020).

Nigeria in the mid-1986, resorted to liberalize monetary policies that brought about a drastic change from all manners of government repressive policy to market based mechanism of the financial sector. After unimpressive take-off in 1986 with direct monetary policy reforms, they failed to meet set targets and objectives of the reform programme such that banking lending rate rose from 17.3% in 1988 to 39.9% in 1993; Spiral inflation rate of 7.8% in 1986 rose to 54.3% in July 1993; Fiscal Deficit/GDP ratio of 5.7% in 1985 which was expected to decrease to 3% and thereafter achieve a fiscal balance and financial stability of the national economy but greatly rose to 9.2% due to excessive domestic government borrowings to finance its fiscal responsibilities by 1993 (CBN, 1994; Ikhide, 1996; Okorounmu, 1994 and Obi *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, a complete indirect monetary policy was gradually introduced from the second half of 1993 (Donli, 2010). But the challenge lied not only in designing a strong value and oriented institutional framework as well as defining result driven monetary policies which can foster increasing capacity development of the financial intermediaries, but also provide easy access to credit for private sector investment. Indeed, a huge availability of resources will greatly enhance the ability of banking sector and other financial institutions and firms to accumulate large amount of savings capital formation which can easily be accessible to private sector investment for turning around of the national economy.

Finally, Nigerian government embarked on various banking reforms over a period of three decades with the aim of enhancing competitiveness in financial services, promoting investment, and ensuring efficiency in resource allocation to the real sector and other sectors of the Nigerian economy (Osa-Afiana & Kelikume, 2015). Several banking sector reforms undertaken in Nigeria by the financial sector regulator

such as bank capital adequacy, availability of credit, exchange rate, monetary policy rate as well as electronic banking which altogether are aimed at ensuring not only the soundness of banking and financial sector stability but also to be very efficient and able to globally compete effectively for the rapid development and growth of the national economy. However, the essence of this study is to investigate the effect of these reforms on the private sector investment as an engine and driver for the rapid economic development and growth of the national economy in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Banking Reform

The important thing about the bank is its role in the creation of financial stability and economic growth among others. The bank is highly regulated to make it conform to the economic functions. Bank reform is aimed at making the banks conform to policies that will create financial stability and economic prosperity. Bank reforms reshapes, revamps, re-direct and correct anomalies or failing tendencies in the bank operations. The primary need for reforms in the financial sector is to develop and consistently maintain a sound and efficient financial system aimed at ensuring that the banks as financial intermediaries can contribute to the agricultural sector through sound allocation of resources (Akpaeti, 2012). Reform has been used to solve a non-profit earning problem in the banking system and to strengthen the overall health of the bank to meet international competition; as well as legislative regulations that are necessary for the optimal banking sector (IGI Global, 2022).

Banking sector reform entails the policy measure designed to deregulate the financial sector system and transform its structure with the view to achieving a liberalized market-oriented system within an appropriate regulatory framework (Oleka, 1993 cited on Eriemo, 2014). In the words of Ebong (2006), financial reforms are deliberate policy response to correct perceived or impending financial crises and subsequent failure. The essence of these reforms are to address issues bordering on governance, risk management and operational inefficiencies in the banking sector. The gist of most banking reforms is to upgrade the capitalization to strengthen the solvency and then lending capacity of the banks to support private sector investment. This is specifically driven by the primary objective of consolidation, competition and convergence in the financial architecture (Deccan, 2004 cited in Jegede, 2014).

Private Sector Investment

The economy of every country has two broad participants which are the private sector and the public sector. The private sector is the part of a country's economic system that is run by individuals and companies, rather than a government entity. Investment by most private sector organizations are done with the intention of making profit.

In Keynesian terminology, investment refers to addition to capital equipment which enables an increase in the production of capital goods (Jhingan, 2002). The term, investment, according to Ibenta (2005), may be defined as accumulation and commitment of fund in financial and real assets with the objective of obtaining income over time. He further noted that it is a commitment of resources made in the hope of realising benefits that are expected to occur over a reasonably long period of time in the future. Investment can also be referred to as the production of capital goods (Heim, 2008). Investment thus includes new plant and equipment, construction of public works like roads, dams, buildings, etc. Investment can be defined as the outlay of money for future use (Agu, 2015).

Investment can be made by the corporate organization for individual stakeholders or directly by the individual in a certain project. This is known as Private Investment. But, when the commitment of funds for productive purposes is done by the government for the betterment of the citizenry, it is called Public Investment.

Private sector investment in Nigeria is faced with some daunting challenges. For decades, Nigeria's economy was characterized by growing dominance of the public sector over the private sector. The private sector faced numerous problems which include; the poor state of physical infrastructure, particularly road networks, electricity and water supply; inadequate credit to the private sector, which has

dove-tailed to high cost of production; insecurity in the country; corruption at various levels; weak institutions, etc. (Okorie & Chikwendu, 2019).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this research is anchored on the theoretical arguments of both classical and neoclassical postulations as mirrored in the seminal work and empirical studies carried out by Schumpeter (1911) and Mckinnon (1973), and Shaw (1973). These distinguished scholars have consistently maintained throughout their arguments that financial development has a strong correlation with growth through investment. They maintain that under the assumption of a well-functioning and result driven market, financial liberalization tremendously enhances efficiency in resource allocation and promotion of competition which greatly results in competitive prices for goods and services.

Indeed, Ronald Mckinnon and Shaw (1973) consolidating on the foundation solidly laid by the seminal work of Schumpeter (1911) propound the financial liberalization theory which they strongly argue that government restrictions on the banking Sector greatly restrain both the quantity and quality of investment. Mckinnon and Shaw (1973) no doubt, are the first to expound the notion of financial liberalisation. Theoretically, an economy with an efficient financial system can easily achieve growth and development through functional and efficient capital allocation. Mckinnon and Shaw (1973) argue that historically, many countries including advanced economy but more especially developing ones have restricted competition in the financial sector with government interventions and regulations.

Strictly based on their argument, a repressed financial sector discourages both savings and investments since the rate of return is very much lower than what can ordinarily be obtained in a competitive market. In a situation like this, the financial intermediaries cannot function at their full capacity since they are tremendously inhibited from efficient channeling of savings into investment which greatly hinders the development of the overall economic system.

The theoretical exposition of these scholars are exceedingly promoted and popularized across the world through several empirical studies carried out by many researchers such as (Pagano, 1993); (king and Levine, 1993); (Fry, 1988); (Levine, 2005); (Bencivenga& Smith, 1999); (Iyoha, 1995) etc whose outcomes of their respective empirical studies are very widely acknowledged by both academics and researchers. They lend their strong supports as they confirm that endogenous growth model is in perfect alignment with liberalization theory. It is their view that financial intermediation under endogenous growth model has a positive effect and nexus on the steady-state growth while government intervention in the financial system has a negative impact on the equilibrium growth rate.

Be that as it may, the financial Liberalization Theory succinctly attributes the poor performance of investment and growth of the national economy in the developing countries to these government interventions in the banking and financial Sectors. Consequently, unlike the Liberalization Theory, these restrictions are sources of the financial repression that results into low interest rate, savings and investments which greatly retard economic growth and development. Hence, the imperativeness for a financial liberalization that frees both the banking sector and financial market from all forms of intervention which greatly promotes market forces of demand and supply, determine efficient allocation of credit for productive investment.

Besides, the theory strongly discourages direct government intervention in economic activities that are detrimental to productive processes, economic growth and development; arguing that its role should be limited to maintenance of law and order, territorial integrity as well creation of relevant institutions for the efficient functioning of the financial system.

Mckinnon and Shaw (1973) are of strong view that liberalization of the financial sector results into great benefits that encompass adequacy of loanable funds for investments through accumulations of large savings' capital formation as well as a sustainable long term economic growth and development.

Indeed, economic growth is thus, expected to drive the growth of the financial sector. In line with this, it will further stimulate and tremendously enhance the process of savings' mobilization as well as efficient allocation of the financial resources for greater increased capacity utilization by the productive investments.

Consequently, however, the policy implications of these theoretical arguments are completely apparent; remove all forms of government repressive tendencies and actions such as high cash reserves and liquidity requirements, direct credit allocations, interest rate ceilings, very outrageous annual fiscal deficits that run into several trillions which to large extent are financed domestically that greatly crowd out private sector investments, regulatory Authority compromise of its duties as well as the destruction of the national currency through constant devaluations of the naira exchange rate, both banking and the financial sectors will be liberalized and allow free market to allocate credit; and thereafter interest rate will adjust to its steady-state equilibrium with investment equilibrate savings in the money market. Besides, wasteful government spending on both noncritical and real sectors of the economy should be completely eliminated so as to tremendously enhance the overall efficiency of investments that stimulate growth and development of the national economy.

Empirical Review

Amagberri and Krokeyi (2024) analyses the effect of changes to Nigeria's banking industry on GDP expansion between 1981 and 2021. The results demonstrate that the banking sector changes in Nigeria contributed significantly to the country's economic development for the better. After the banking industry was consolidated, the liquidity ratio was found to have a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth, whereas before the reforms it had no effect at all. In addition, prior to the consolidation of the banking system, the cash reserve ratio had a negative and statistically negligible effect on economic expansion. Cash reserve ratio's effect on GDP growth was found to be positive and non-statistically significant following the change. A positive and statistically significant effect of monetary policy rate on economic growth was also shown in the years prior to the implementation of banking sector reforms. The reform had a considerable negative effect on economic growth as a result of the monetary policy rate. In order to maintain the effectiveness and efficiency of banks and the broader banking system, frequent reforms to the banking industry are necessary. To improve liquidity, and thus economic growth, the cash reserve ratio should be lowered

Abubakar (2023) examined the effects of automated teller machine (ATM) on user satisfaction in Nigeria: A study of united bank for Africa in Sokoto metropolis: The Nigerian Banking sector over the years has been experiencing significant changes and development in its Information and Communication Technology. Among the development is the introduction of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) that intends to decongest the banking halls as customers now can go to any nearest ATM outfit to consummate their banking transactions such as: cash withdrawal, cash deposit, bill payments, and transfer of fund between accounts. The research was carried through across-sectional survey design which questioned respondents on ATM services. The population of study mainly constituted of customers of United Bank for Africa within Sokoto metropolis. The sample in this study consisted of 100 respondents who are users of the ATM services. The data collected was analyzed by use of multiple logistic regression analysis. The findings revealed that, the impact of ATM services in terms of their perceived ease of use, transaction cost and service security is positive and significant. However, the result also indicates that the impact of ATM services in terms of availability of money is positive but insignificant.

Bawa, Chiebonam and Abdulsalami (2021) investigated the effect of banking sector reforms on Nigeria economic growth for competitive global market from 1981-2020. The data were analysed using the cointegration test. The findings revealed that among others that credit allocation to private sector had a salutary trend from 1981 to 2006 and later experienced a gradual upward movement from 2007 to 2020. This shows that banking sector has contributed to the real sector of the economy through credit given to private sector. It confirms that credit is significant to economic growth.

Waleru (2023), who looked into the effect of banking sector reforms (BSR). The research included panel data from 13 publicly-traded deposit money institutions from 2010 to 2019. The Hausman test was used to compare the best-fitting option among random effects, fixed effects, and pooled estimates. This study found a positive and statistically significant effect of credit allocation on ROE for DMBs, a negative and statistically significant relationship between ROE and deposit mobilisation and the capital adequacy ratio, and a positive but statistically insignificant effect of asset quality on ROE. With regards to deposit

mobilization and credit distribution, the report suggested that the Central Bank of Nigeria increase the minimum capitalization of banks and its monitoring function on DMBs. The effects of financial sector reforms on GDP expansion in Ghana were studied by Antwi-

Bosiako (2022) used quantitative methods, including those that were quasi-experimental. The outcome demonstrated that changes made to the financial sector had a substantial impact on Ghana's GDP growth. To help Ghana's economy thrive, the research suggested revamping the financial sector to prioritize quality over quantity.

Folake and Johnson (2021) used the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) to analyze the progression of reforms in Nigeria's banking sector and its relationship to GDP growth from 1980 to 2016. Those findings demonstrated the importance of a change in Nigeria's financial sector to the country's GDP growth. As the study found, improvements in the financial sector are necessary for both economic growth and the smooth functioning of market intermediaries, which the regulatory body and policymaker should actively push.

Maurice (2020) used ordinary least square multiple regression analysis. Restructuring the country's financial system had a statistically significant negative impact on Nigeria's GDP growth. There should be adequate time between reform periods to allow for proper preparation, according to the study's recommendation.

Ezeocha (2020) investigated the effect of banking sector reforms on economic growth in Nigeria. The study used the Gross Domestic Product as proxy for growth while the explanatory variables were Interest rate, Credit allocation to the private sector and Investment rate. The results analyses using the ordinary least square multiple regression Method, showed that there is a negative relationship between the Loan and the Gross domestic product which signifies that they are inversely related. More so, there is a significant relationship between banking reforms and real sector financing.

Okoyan and Ayunku (2020) examined the relationship between banking sector reforms and money market performance in Nigeria using an annual data spanning the period 2004 to 2018. The study adopted commercial paper as a proxy for money market performance, while banking reforms was proxied by credit to the private sector (CPS), broad money supply (M2) and total bank deposit (TD). The OLS was employed for data analysis. The results showed that credit to the private sector (CPS) and total deposits (TD) had a positive and significant effect on the volume of commercial paper (CP) traded on the Nigerian Stock Exchange; whereas total money supply had a negative and significant effect.

Okoi, Ocheni and Orok (2019) examined the impact of banking sector reforms on economic growth in Nigeria using the annual time series data for forty six years spanning from 1970 to 2015. The study captured bank reforms as interest rate spread, exchange rate, bank capital base, and corporate governance disclosure index. The data were analyzed using Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) test. The results found that interest rate spread was correctly signed and adequately predictive of economic growth indicator studied while other exogenous variables did not impact positively on gross domestic product growth in Nigeria. Further result indicated existence of a long-run relationship among these variables and short run adjustment effects.

Oniore and Okoli (2019) examined the impact of electronic banking on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2006 to 2017 using time series quarterly data. The study adopted Ordinary Least Squares as main tool of analysis. The estimated regression equation showed that in the long-run, all the variables are correctly signed, except inter-bank transfer that is negatively signed. The policy implication of the findings is that e-banking has gradual positive impacts on performance of banks in Nigeria and hence could

Gap in Literature

The review of empirical studies has shown positive effect of banking reforms on investment. Most of the studies hardly capture reform variables succinctly to address the drastic change in the banking sector operations that constitute the reform issues and/or targets thereby creating a knowledge Gap. The present study aims to build in dummies to capture the periods of reform for each of the reform targets. These dummies imply indication of the periods within which the policy change occurs.

Most of the studies on banking reform issues reviewed are predominant in examining their effects on economic growth, financial deepening, financial inclusion and less of investment. The present study will therefore, investigate the effect of banking sector reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. This is premised on the assertion that the private sector is not only the engine but also the major driver of economic activities among developing countries including Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted the *ex-post facto* research design because the data already exist in various international and national publications. The data were analyzed with econometric techniques involving Augmented Dicker Fuller tests for unit roots and the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) approach which is capable of handling both stationary at level I(0) and first difference I(1).

Model Specification

The model used for this investigation is the adaption and modification of the work of:

The model is stated thus:

Uchenna and James (2016)

$$PI = f(TBC, CPS)$$

Where:

PI = private sector investment

TBC = Total Bank capital base representing bank reforms

CPS= Credit to private sector

The Model is modified as follows:

$$PI = f(TBC, CPS, EXR)$$

Where:

PI = private sector investment

TBC = Total Bank capital base representing bank reforms

CPS= Credit to private sector

EXR= Exchange rate

The Econometric Equation Form of the Model is:

$$PI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TBC + \beta_2 CPS + \beta_3 EXR + \mu - - - - - 1$$

μ = Stochastic Disturbance (Error Term)

f = Functional Relationship

β_0 = Intercept of Relationship in the Model Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3,$ = are the Coefficients of the Independent Variables

DATA ANALYSIS

Unit Root Test

Table 1 Summary Unit Root test for Stationarity

Variables	At Level 1(0)	At First Difference 1(1)	At Second Difference	Order of Integration	Probability
PI	-3.730558			1(0)	0.0039
TBC	-4.561864			1(0)	0.0112
CPS		-4.595801		1(1)	0.0016
EXR	-5.814004			1(0)	0.0022

Source: Researcher’s Estimation using Eviews 9.0

The study employed the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Unit root test technique to ascertain the stationarity of the variables of the time series data. The Augmented Dickey Fuller is one of the most

prominent unit root test techniques and has been used to determine whether the variables are stationary series or non-stationary series.

From the summary of the result, it can be seen that there is a mixed order of integration, that is I(0) and I(1). In such circumstances, it becomes necessary to make use of the ARDL bound testing technique for cointegration test and ARDL estimation technique for estimating the coefficients of the econometric model. This is because the commonly used Engel- Granger, and Johansen cointegration techniques are only employed when the order of integration of each variable in the model is I(1).

Furthermore, table 1 above showed that PI, TBC and EXR were stationary at level, I(0), while CPS was stationary at 1st difference, I(1).

Cointegration Test -The ARDL Bound Test

The ARDL bound testing technique was to test if the variables in the econometric model were cointegrated or not. The robustness of the ARDL cointegration bound test has been affirmed by many studies in establishing if long run relationship exists between the dependent variable and the independent variables in the econometric model. It is known to be superior to Engel- Grange, and Johansen cointegration techniques and employed in situations of mixed order integration (Pesaran and Shin, 1999, and Pesaran et al. 2001).

Its superiority is known to lie in its flexibility as it can be used with I(0) or I(1) variables, or both, works well with small sample data, and provides unbiased estimation of long run relationship and long run parameters. By Distributed Lag (DL) variables we imply lagged values of observed exogenous predictor variables while Autoregressive (AR) variables are lagged values of observed endogenous response variables.

Two sets of critical values were given by Pesaran and Pesaran (1996a), and Pesaran et al. (2001) in the bound test. These include a set for the lower bound I(0) values presuming that all the variables are I(0) and the other for the upper bound I(1) values presuming that all the variables are I(1). The variables in the model are said to be cointegrated if the F-statistic is greater than the upper bound values. The implication would be that a long run relationship exists between the variables. In the situation where the F-statistic so reported is lower than the lower bound values, then there is no cointegration. There is an inconclusive result if the F-statistic value lies in-between the lower and the upper bounds

Table 2. Result of the ARDL (Bounds) Test for Cointegration for Banking Sector Reforms and Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

ARDL Bounds Test
 Date: 03/19/26 Time: 16:46
 Sample: 1985 2025
 Included observations: 36
 Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	5.710216	5

Critical Value Bounds

Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.26	3.35
5%	2.62	3.79
2.5%	2.96	4.18
1%	3.41	4.68

Source: Eviews 9.0

The bound test is shown in Table 2. The result compared the F-statistics with the critical bound values. The F-statistics is 5.710216. The results showed that the F-statistic is greater than the lower bounds at 2.62 and upper bounds at 3.79 of the critical values at 0.05 level of significance. The implication is that there is a cointegration or long run relationship between banking sector reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria.

Analyses of ARDL Long Run Coefficients and Error Correction

Having established the presence of long-run relationships in banking sector reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria, this section explained the nature of the relationship as well as the speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium. The results from CointEq (-1) from the cointegrating form is used to explain the speed of adjustment. The nature of the relationship is explained by the long run coefficients.

Analyses of Long Run Effects of Banking Sector Reforms and Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Table3: Model of the long Run relationship Between Banking Sector Reforms and Private Sector

Investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Cointegrating Form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(PI(-1))	1.039810	0.277245	3.750509	0.0331
D(TBC)	0.002621	0.001024	2.560316	0.0832
D(TBCL(-1))	-0.004492	0.001097	-4.094364	0.0263
D(TBC(-2))	0.002671	0.001934	1.380650	0.2613
D(CPS)	0.010966	0.003202	3.424595	0.0417
D(CPS(-1))	-0.006046	0.002548	-2.372973	0.0982
D(CPS(-2))	-0.006007	0.001941	-3.094517	0.0535
D(EXR)	-0.011568	0.009225	-1.253994	0.2987
D(EXR(-1))	0.044598	0.019878	2.243635	0.1106
D(EXR(-2))	-0.014777	0.017272	-0.855557	0.4551
CointEq(-1)	-0.100379	0.184168	-0.545042	0.6236

$$\text{Cointeq} = \text{PI} - (0.0402 * \text{TBC} + 0.3049 * \text{CPS} - 1.1362 * \text{EXR} - 10.4583)$$

Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TBC	0.040218	0.068843	0.584199	0.6001
CPS	0.304891	0.579615	0.526022	0.6353
EXR	-1.136185	2.285294	-0.497172	0.6532
C	-10.458289	17.339872	-0.603135	0.5890

Source: Eviews 9.0

Analysis of the nature and significance of the relationship between banking sector reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria is shown on Table 3. From the results, the error correction of -0.1004 at a probability value of 0.6236 is shown. The coefficient has a negative sign suggesting the possibility of a return on long run equilibrium. However, since the p.value is greater than 0.05, it indicates an insignificant speed of adjustment. This suggests that banking sector reforms does not have a significant long-run policy effect on the private sector investment in Nigeria. This implies that banking sector reforms has not played instrumental roles in driving private sector investment in Nigeria. The long-run coefficients of regression confirmed the insignificant long-run effects since all the banking sector reforms variables (TBC, CPS, EXR) have p.values that are greater than 0.05.

Estimation of Short Run Effect of Banking Sector Reforms on Private Sector Investment

The short-run effects of banking sector reforms on the private sector investment are analyzed using the Auto-regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) model. The ARDL model has become the most suitable regression tool when the variables were integrated into a mixture of level 1(0) and the first difference 1(1). The statistical tools for the interpretation are the coefficient of regression, and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The statistical significance is confirmed using the t-statistics for the coefficient of regression, and F-statistics for the coefficient of determination.

Short run Effect of Banking Sector Reforms on Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Table 4: Short Run Model of the Relationship between Banking Sector Reforms and Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
PI(-1)	0.795661	0.501634	1.586139	0.2109
PI(-2)	1.655111	1.630442	1.015130	0.3848
PI(-3)	-1.915205	1.260089	-1.519897	0.2259
TBC	0.761345	0.447073	1.702957	0.1871
TBC(-1)	1.554731	1.268706	1.225446	0.3078
TBC(-2)	2.723949	0.412514	6.603283	0.0071
CPS	7.196438	1.972018	3.649275	0.0355
CPS(-1)	7.650823	3.589890	2.131214	0.1229
CPS(-2)	6.827734	1.777909	3.840316	0.0311
CPS(-3)	7.051449	2.421617	2.911877	0.0619
EXR	-15.74800	5.170556	-3.045707	0.0556
EXR(-1)	-53.75272	13.01989	-4.128507	0.0258
EXR(-2)	-28.89880	13.53544	-2.135046	0.1224
EXR(-3)	12.51968	9.346894	1.339448	0.2729
C	-971.9103	341.9209	-2.842500	0.0655
R-squared	0.999944			
Adjusted R-squared	0.999461			
F-statistic	2067.766			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000015			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.676546			

Source: Eviews 9.0

The ARDL result of the short-run effect of banking sector reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria is presented in Table 4. The coefficient regression of the dependent variable (Private Sector Investment) showed positive effects at first and second years, but negative effect in the third year. However, the p.values is greater than ($p > 0.05$) 0.05 level of significance. This supposes that private sector investment is not an endogenous factor in the model.

Table 4 further revealed that the Total Bank Capital (TBC) has a positive relationship with private sector investment in all the periods from level to 2 years. However, only the lag 2 coefficient of TBC had significant relationship with private sector investment in Nigeria. This supposes that a unit increase in TBC by the bank management will bring about 2.72 units of rise in the private sector investment in Nigeria.

Similarly, the credit to private sector showed positive relationship with private sector investment in all the periods within the short-term frame spanning level to lag 3. Nonetheless, the p.values indicates significant relationships at level, and lag 2. This indicates that a unit increase in credit to private sector leads to 7.19 and 6.82 units of fall in PI at level and after three (3) years, respectively. The coefficient of exchange rate to private sector investment relationship showed a mixed effect of

negative relationships from initial period to lag 2 and positive relationship at lag 3. However, these effects are only significant at initial period (level) and lag 1 (after year 1) and insignificant other years from lag 2 to 3. This means that exchange rate has a significant short-term negative (EXR = -53.75272, $p = 0.0258$) effect on private sector investment in Nigeria. This suggests that a unit increased in exchange rate will bring about fall in the private sector investment within the short term period especially in the first and second year period.

On the overall, the adjusted coefficient of determination (Adj R^2) revealed that about 99% of the change in the private sector investment can be explained by banking sector reforms in Nigeria. This is confirmed by a significantly significant p.value of 0.000 from the F-statistics (2067.766). The Durbin-Watson statistics of 2.67 suggests a suspicion on the confounding influence of trends on the reliability of the model.

CONCLUSION

The result of the analysis revealed that there is a cointegration or long run relationship between Banking Sector Reforms and Private Sector Investment in Nigeria. Total bank capital has a positive relationship with private sector investment in all the periods. Credit to private sector had positive relationship with private sector investment in all the periods and exchange rate has a significant short-term negative effect on private sector investment in Nigeria. This suggests that a unit increased in exchange rate will bring about fall in the private sector investment within the short term period especially in the first and second year period.

This connotes that banking sector is the driver of the private sector investment in Nigeria. An active and efficient banking sector is essential to enhances growth of the private sector of Nigerian economy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Amongst the recommendations is that monetary authority should frame and implement policies for regular review and increasing or classification of bank capital base. This will inform the nature and level of operations for such banks. Bank management should review their credit profile and propensity to lending on regular bases. The monetary authority on another hand should discourage banks from granting unproductive loans by way of penal charge. The exchange rate reform in Nigeria has being found to lack short run dynamic influence in the private sector. It is recommended that he monetary authority should unify the exchange rate markets in Nigeria to have only one exchange rate for all monetary exchange.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, K. (2023). The effects of automated teller machine (ATM) on user satisfaction in Nigeria: A study of united bank for Africa in Sokoto metropolis: *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting* 3(5): 7-46
- Adelegan, A. E. (2018). Private domestic investment, domestic credit to the private sector and economic performance: Nigeria in perspective. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 9(3), 22-31.
- Afolabi, J.A. (2004). Implications of the consolidation of banks for the Nigerian banking system. A paper presented at the NDIC organized workshop for FICAN, Enugu, Nigeria.
- Aftab, N., Jebran, K., Ullah, I. & Awais, M. (2016). Impact of interest rate on private sector credit: Evidence from Pakistan. *Jinnah Business Review*, 4(1), 47-52.
- Agu, O. C. (2015). Determinants of private investment in Nigeria: An econometric analysis. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, III (4), 1 – 14.
- Ajayi, M. (2005). Banking sector reforms and bank consolidation: Conceptual Framework. *CBN Bullion*, 29(2): 2 – 10.
- Akinkoye, E.Y. & Oyelami, L.O. (2014). Bank recapitalization and real sector performance: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Finance and Banking Studies*, 5(1), 126 -136.

- Akpaeti, A. J. (2012). Does financial sector reforms affect agricultural investments in NIGERIA? A cointegration and VAR approach. *International Journal of Food and Agricultural Economics*, 1(2) 13-28.
- Akpaeti, J. A. (2013). Does financial sector reforms affect agricultural investments in Nigeria? A cointegration and VAR approach. *International Journal of Food and Agricultural Economics*, 1(2), 13-28.
- Akpan, E.S (2011), Nigerian financial institutions in David O. Mbat (Ed), *Topical Issues in Finance* (pp 24-71). Calabar, University of Calabar Press.
- Akpansung, A.O. & Gidigbi, M.O. (2014). Recent banking reforms in Nigeria: Implications on sectoral credit allocation and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 5(13), 91 – 104.
- Ali, J. I., Nwakoby, C., Okonkwo, I. V. & Yua, H. (2020). Effect of banking sector reforms on the growth of manufacturing sector in developing economies: A study of Nigeria 1986 to 2018. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 8(4), 11-38.
- Allen, F. & Gale, D. (2000). *Comparing Financial Systems*, Cambridge and London: MIT Press.
- Allen, F. & Gale, D. (2003). Competition and Financial Stability. *Journal of Money, Credit, and Banking*, 36, 433-480.
- Amaegberi, M & Krokeyi W.S (2024). Banking Sector Reforms and Economic Growth in Nigeria: *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences Vol 14 No 6*
- Andabai, P. W. & Bina, P. A. (2019). E-banking and its impact on economic growth in Nigeria (2000-2018). *Global Journal of Education, Humanities and Management Science*, 1(2), 11 – 19.
- Angahar, J. S. (2013). Banking Sector Reforms And Economic Performance: Analysis Using Credit To Private Sector. *IJTEMT, II(IV)*, 14 - 22.
- Ani, W.U., Ugwunta, D. O., & Okanya, O. (2013). The Effect of foreign exchange reforms on financial deepening: Evidence from Nigeria. *American Journal of Business and*
- Anyanwu, C.M. (2010). Overview of current banking sector reform and the real sector of the Nigerian Economy. Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review 48(4), December, 2010.
- Athanasoglou, P.P., Brissimis, S.N. & Delis, M.D. (2005). Bank-Specific, Industry-Specific and Macroeconomic Determinants of Bank Profitability. *Bank of Greece Working Paper*, No. 25.
- Azumah, C. Y., Owusu-Ansah, A., Amewu, G. & Ohemeng, W. (2023). The effect of banking sector reforms on interest rate spread: Evidence from Ghana. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23322039.2023.2175463>
- Babatunde, O. & Ogebeide, S (2017). E-Banking in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(6): 15 – 24.
- Bader, M., & Malawi, A. I. (2010). Impact of interest rate on investment In Jordan. *Jkau: Eco. & Adm*, 199-209.
- Banday, U. J. & Anaja (2019). Twin deficit hypotheses and reverse causality: A Case study of China. Palgrave Communications Humanities/Social Sciences/Business, 5-93.
- Bawa, I., Chiebonam, O. G. & Abdulsalami, Z. (2021). Analysis of Banking Sector Reforms on Nigeria Economic
- Bawa, I., Chiebonam, O. G. & Abdulsalami, Z. (2021). Analysis of Banking Sector Reforms on Nigeria Economic Growth: An Issue for Competitive Global Market (1980-2020). *International Journal of Advanced Research in Statistics, Management and Finance*, 8(2), 45 – 58.
- Beck, T., Demirgüç-Kunt, A. & Levine, R. (2003). Bank Concentration and Crises. *NBER Working Paper* No. 9921. Retrieved from <http://www.nber.org/papers/W9921>.
- Beck, T., Demirgüç-Kunt, A. & Levine, R. (2004). *Bank Concentration and Fragility: Impact and Mechanics*. Paper retrieved from <http://www.nber.org/books/risk/beck-et-al12-15-04.pdf>.
- Benecivenga, V.R. & Smith B.D. (1991). Financial intermediation and endogenous growth. *Review of Economic Studies*, 58(2), 195-209.

- Berger, A. & Udell, G. (1996). Relationship Lending and Lines of Credit in Small Firm Finance. *Journal of Business*, 68 (3), 65 – 97.
- Bernanke, B. S. (1983). Nonmonetary Effects of the Financial Crisis in Propagation of the Great Depression. *American Economic Review*, 73(3), 257-276.
- Boyd, J. H. & Runkle, D. E. (1999). Size and Performance of Banking Firms: Testing the predictions of Theory. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 31(7), 67-78
- Brock, T. (2020). Private sector definition. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/p/private-sector.asp>.
- Cañonero, G. (1997). Bank Concentration and the Supply of Credit in Argentina. *IMF Working Paper*, WP/97/40, April.
- CBN. (1994). Economic and Financial Review, 31(4), December, 1994.
- CBN. (2004). Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review, December 2004.
- CBN. (2010). Central Bank of Nigeria Economics and Financial Review, 48(4), December 2010.
- Chong, B.S. (1991). Effects of Interstate Banking on Commercial Banks' Risk and Profitability. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 73, 78-84.
- Daily Independent Newspapers, (2020). Undue government spending. Daily Independent Newspaper May5, 2020.
- Daily Trust Newspaper (2022). Nation borrowed ₦ 225 trillion in the Last 20 years and Earned ₦115 trillion during the same period, Daily Trust Newspapers July 13, 2022.
- Demirguc-kunt, A. & Levine, R. (2000). Bank Concentrations Cross Country Evidence. London City: McGraw-hills Publishers. Retrieved from <http://www.globalpolicy.org/socecon/tncs/mergers/imfbankcons.htm>.
- Demsetz, R. S. & Strahan, P. E. (1999). The consolidation of the financial services industry: Causes, consequences, and implications for the future. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 23(2-4), 135-194.
- Dixit, A. K., & Pindyck, R. S. (1994). Investment under Uncertainty. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400830176>
- Domar, E.D. ([1948). The problem of capital accumulation. *American Economic Review*. 38, 777-94.
- Donli, J. G. (2010). An overview of Nigeria's economic reforms. CBN Economic & Financial Review, 42(4), 14 – 28. <http://library.cbn.gov.ng:8092/jspui/bitstream/123456789/689/1/An%20overview%20of%20nigeria%27s%20economic%20reforms%20%282%29.pdf>
- Ebong, B. B. (2006). Banking sector reforms: Opportunities and challenges. *Union Digest*, 10, 12 – 18.
- Ekpo, U. N. (2016). Determinants of private investment in Nigeria: An empirical exploration. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 7(11), 56 – 76.
- Eriemo, N. O. (2014). Banking sector reforms and critical factors in Nigeria's economic growth process. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(17), 192 – 198.
- Ezeocha, C. M. (2020). Banking sector reforms and economic growth: the case for Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Science and Entrepreneurship*, 19(7), 315 – 329.
- Ezeocha, C. M. (2020). Banking sector reforms and economic growth: The case for Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Science and Entrepreneurship*, 19(7), 315 - 329.
- Folake, B. R. & Johnson, A. O. (2021). Financial Sector Reforms and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies*. 3(1), 135 – 145.
- Freund, R. J. & Littell, R. C. (2000). *SAS System for Regression* (Third edition). Cary, NC: SAS Institute.
- Fry, M.J. (1988). Money, Interest and Banking in Economic Development. The John Hopkins University Press, Baltimore and London.
- Gbenga, O., James, S. O. & Adeyinka, A. J. (2019). Determinant of Private Sector Credit and Its Implication on Economic Growth in Nigeria: 2000-2017. Retrieved from <https://www.cribfb.com/journal/index.php/aesr/article/view/242/299>.
- Ghatak, S. & Siddiki, J.U. (2001). The use of the ARDL approach in estimating virtual exchange rates in India, *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 28 (5), 573-583.

- Gidigbi, M. (2017). An assessment of the impact of banking reforms on economic growth and bank performance in Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 8(2), 143 – 162.
- Gidigbi, M. O. (2017). An Assessment of the impact of banking reforms on economic growth and bank performance in Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 8(2), 143 – 160.
- Harrod, R. F. (1948). *Towards a Dynamic Economics*. London: Macmillan
- Heim, J. J. (2008). The Investment function: determinants of demand for investment. *Working Papers in Economics*.
- Ibenta, S. O. N. (2005). *Investment analysis and financial management strategy*. Enugu: Institute for Development Studies.
- Idoko, C. U., Ibrahim, Y. & Bala, P. D. (2015). E – banking reform and national development in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Human Social Science*, XV(II- I), 1 – 5.
- Kamasa, K., Mochiah, I., Doku, A. K., & Forson, P. (2020). The impact of financial sector reforms on foreign direct investment in an emerging economy: Empirical evidence from Ghana. *Journal of Humanities and Applied Social Sciences*, 2(4), 271 – 284.
- King, R. & Levine, R. (1993). Finance entrepreneurship and growth. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 32, 1-30.
- Njoku, C. O., Nwadike, E. C. & Azuama, G. U. (2020). Effect of electronic banking on the economic growth of Nigeria [2009-2018]. *The International Journal of Business Management and Technology*, 4(3), 196 – 219.
- Nkemakolam, A. C. (2017). Effect of bank capital reforms on economic growth of Nigeria: 1986 to 2013. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews*, 7(1), 220 –228.
- Nnanna, O. J. & Dogo, N. (1998). Structural Reform, Monetary Policy and Financial Deepening: The Nigerian Experience. *Economic and Financial Review*, 36(2), 1 - 29.
- Nteegah, Udeorah, S., & Owede, V. M. (2017). Banking sector consolidation: Possible effects for sectoral credit allocation and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Science and Economics Invention*, 3(1), 91 – 101.
- Nwakoby, C. & Alajekwu U. B. (2016). Effect of monetary policy on Nigerian stock market performance. *International Journal of scientific research and management*, 4(9), 4530 – 4542.
- Ohiomah, S. S. (2021). Bank reforms in Nigeria: It’s impact on bank lending to the manufacturing sector. *African Scholar Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 23 (6), 175 - 186.
- Okafor, K. (2019). Current perspectives in the recovery of bank loans in Nigeria. *International Journal of Family Business and Management*, 3(3), 1-10.
- Okoi, I. O., Ocheni, S. I. & Orok, A. B. (2019). Impact of banking sector reforms on economic growth in Nigeria. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 154(2), 230-240.
- Okorie, G. C. & Chikwendu, N. F. (2019). Does private sector credit impact on private sector investment in Nigeria? *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, VI(XII), 23 – 28.
- Okoro, C. O., Nzotta, M., Egungwu, I. & Alajekwu, U. B. (2019). Effect of public investments on private sector investment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Management Fields*, 3(3), 55 – 68.
- Okorounmu, T. O. (1994). Fiscal Operations of the Federal Government: Policies and Strategies since 1986; *CBN Economic and Financial Review*, 31(4), December 1994.
- Okoyan, K., & Ayunku, P. (2020). Banking sector reforms and money market performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 5(2), 164 – 170.
- Onodugo, V. A. Anowor, O. F., Ukwani, N. O. & Ibiam, F. O. (2014). Bank credit and private sector investment: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Sciences*, 3(2), 82-92.
- Onoh, J. O. & Iheanacho, E. (2017). Banking reforms and credit creation in the Nigerian banking sector: Pre-reform era versus post-reform era. *IIARD International Journal of Banking and Finance Research*, 3(1), 15 – 39.
- Osa-Afiana, L. O. & Kelikume, I. (2015). The impact of banking sector reforms and credit supply on agricultural sector. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 50 (5), 71-84.

- Sathye, M. (2002). The Impact of Foreign Banks on Market Concentration: The Case of India. *Applied Econometrics and International Development*, 2-1, 7-20. Retrieved from <http://www.ideas.repec.org/s/ea/aeinde.html>.
- Schumpeter, J.A. (1912). Financial development and economic growth: An egg and chicken problem? *International Economics*, 8(3), 443-454.
- Selway, J. & Templeman, K. (2012). The Myth of Consociationalism? Conflict Reduction in Divided Societies. *Comparative Political Studies*. 45. 1542-1571.
- Sesay, B & Abdulai B.S. (2017). Monetary Policy effects on private sector investment: Evidence from Sierra Leone. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 7(1), 476-488.
- Shaw, E. (1973). *Financial deepening in economic development*, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Solow, R.M. (1956). Letter to Evsey Domar. 21 March. Robert Solow Papers, Box 53. David M. Rubenstein Rare Book and Manuscript Library, Duke University.
- Toby, A & Zaagha, A. S. (2020). Central bank policy and private sector funding in Nigeria: A multi-variant study. *RSU Journal of Strategic and Internet Business*, 5(1), 899-923.
- Uba, C. (2006). Dially Sun, Thursday. June 22, pp.39.
- Waleru, A.H. (2023). Banking Sector Reform and Financial Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*. 24(1), 352 – 362.
- Zardashty, G. R. (2014). ‘The impact of real exchange rate uncertainty on private investment in Iran’, Kuwait Chapter of *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 3(10), 1-2.